

The impact of Country of Origin on Perceived Quality & Value: Empirical Evidence in the automobiles industry in Iran

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Abstract: This manuscript explores the effect of Country-Of-Origin on perceived quality & perceived value. In automotive among Iranian consumers. Consumer attitudes to local and foreign products and the likely "country-of-origin" effect in Buy "Local" and "Made In ..." companies are surveyed. So, the importance of understanding differential consumer perception and evaluation of products has been well illustrated in consumer behaviour literature. The hypotheses of this research cover four main cores. Structured questionnaires and simple random sampling were used. A sample of 381 Iranian students in Selective University evaluate perceived quality associated with the value of vehicles came from Korea and Iran. Questionnaires were distributed with simple random sampling method Data were analyzed based on Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS, V. 21). The author recommends future researchers examine the relations of the research in studies focusing on other products, markets.

Keywords: Country-Of-Origin, perceived value, perceived quality

INTRODUCTION

A products country of origin (COO) is often used as an extrinsic cue to provide consumers with a basis for purchase decisions (Bilkey and Nes, 1982; Cordell, 1992; Erickson et al, 1984; Han, 1989; Hong & Wyer, 1989, 1990; Thorelli et al, 1989). Since the pioneering finding of Schooler (1965) that the COO of a product can have an effect on a consumer's opinion of the product, extensive research on the influence of COO on product evaluation of consumers has been reported in the literature (Johansson, Douglas and Nonaka, 1985). However, research findings on how COO affects product evaluation are largely inconclusive (Bilkey and Nes, 1982; Ozsomer and Cavusgil, 1991). Till date there is significant amount of researches on the relations between consumer behavior and product's COO (Miranda & Parkvithee, 2013) and it is the major focus of research (Seidenfuss et al., 2013). An example to indicate the importance of this concept; one of the most famous scientific journals such as "International Marketing Review", published a special volume focused on the COO phenomenon directly (2008, Vol. 25, No. 4) (Magnusson et al., 2011). COO image is an important extrinsic product cue, and researches show that it affects consumer perceptions, purchase intension and overall evaluations of the product (Lee & Lee, 2011). The COO literature has consistently reported biases toward non-domestic products due to COO effects (Martín & Cervinˆo, 2011), especially when the consumer has low knowledge with foreign brands (Moradi & Zarei, 2012). In international environment, several studies show that COO influences the key dimensions of brand equity (Anisimova, 2013; Moradi & Zarei, 2012). The literature of (Ha-Brookshire & Yoon, 2012) shows that COO plays a major role in consumers' decision-making processes and influences how consumers view and evaluate product attributes.

Product origin has become a more complicated construct due to multi-national production relates to more than just one COO cue (Seidenfuss et al., 2013). Product may have separated dimensions such as country of assembly (COA) (Ha-

Brookshire & Yoon, 2012), country of components and parts (COC) (Ha-Brookshire & Yoon, 2012), and country of design (COD) (Seidenfuss et al., 2013), country of brand (COB) (Anisimova, 2013) and country of manufacture (COM) (Moradi & Zarei, 2012). Statistically significant COO effects have been documented for general products, categories of products even for certain brands. Studies prove this point, that "made in" label is very important for consumer while evaluating product (Moradi & Zarei, 2012). Country of manufacture serves as an important informational cue in influencing decisions and purchases (Kabadayi & Lerman, 2011)

Perceived quality is much on the minds of academicians and practitioners today (e.g., Aaker & Jacobson, 1994; Carman, 1990; Forker, 1991; Gottlieb, Grewal, and Brown 1994; Herbig & O'Hara, 1994; Teas 1993; Zifko-Baliga, 1995). The importance of perceived quality to firms is unequivocal. Research has demonstrated that the perceived quality can influence various desirable organizational outcomes, e.g., customer satisfaction, purchase intention, customer value (e.g., Bitner, 1990; Engel & Blackwell, 1982; Gutman & Alden, 1985; Olson, 1977). Also, an understanding of consumer perceptions of quality is necessary if efforts in the workplace are to be directed toward factors that are important to the consumer. Hence, the knowledge of consumer perceptions of quality is useful for the effective management of people in a quality organization environment (Forker, 1991; Juran, 1988). The widely-acknowledged importance of the construct has prompted scholars from a wide variety of disciplines to investigate various factors that can influence the perceived quality of products. Consequently, the influence of various marketing cues on the perceived quality of products has been widely studied (Aaker & Jacobson, 1994; Dodds, Monroe & Grew al, 1991; Jacob, Olson & Haddock, 1971; Wheatley & Chiu, 1977). Wang, 2013 and Rundh, (2011), confirm that previous studies have concluded that PV has significantly influenced the purchasing intention, PQ provides added value for the consumer and PQ positively influences PV (Edward & Sahadev, 2011). In the same context, the literature review of

Wang, (2013), reports that multiple studies have found a correlation between PQ and PV. “Value” is one of the most widely and frequently used words in various disciplines of social science (O’Sullivan & McCallig, 2012). In the marketing domain, value has been considered a key concept in understanding and predicting customer behavior (Choo et al., 2012). Customer value is the key determinant of marketing decisions (Munnukka et al., 2013). The concept of PV has become one of the most popular approaches among business managers and marketing researchers (Chen, 2013). The creation of value for customers has long been recognized as “the fundamental basis for all marketing activity” and an effective source of competitive advantage in promoting profit growth and ensuring long-term success (Chen, 2013). The majority of researchers agree that value is a trade-off between the benefits and sacrifices components (Hakola, 2013).

Various studies to address the issue of the number of country image dimensions reflected through consumer product quality evaluations have been reported in the literature (Crawford and Garland, 1988; Howard, 1989; Roth and Romeo, 1992; Martin and Eroglu, 1993). The multidimensionality of the country construct and its impact on consumer product evaluations, however, have largely been ignored. As the design quality and product quality pertain to two different aspects of the quality dimension, the hybrid product phenomenon is ideally suited to the testing of the validity of multiple quality dimensions in consumer product evaluations. Nations are likely to differ with respect to their design and assembly capabilities. For instance, Germany is well known for her product engineering and therefore products incorporating German engineering are likely to be perceived as high quality products.

The economy of Iran, the study setting, has been continually growing for the last two decades. Iran has been inundated with a large number of foreign brands covering every conceivable product category, from food-stuffs, toys and apparel, to automobiles, computers, and cellular phones. Foreign competitors from around the world, including Korean firms, have been actively seeking a market share in Iran. Like the consumers of several other developing countries, the consumers in Iran have enthusiastically adopted the Western consumer culture. Since the major industrialized countries are the top players in the Iran market, consumers in Iran are familiar with and have formed opinions about the products of the top industrial countries. This research paper chose to apply on one of the largest trading (vehicles trading) and its case is one of the rarely highest importing countries (Iran). Although, the four decades of research around the construct of COO, but the marketing research still in-need to additional researches, with more study for different variables and with the application on a lot of diverse markets. This research paper may be a contribution in that context.

LITERATURE & HYPOTHESES

COUNTRY-OF-ORIGIN COO

The definitions of COO are diverse. The previous definitions may be categorized in two categories; source-based and perception-based. The researchers who define COO from the source-based viewpoint, define it as the country of: “manufacture (Kabadayi & Lerman, 2011; Marti´n & Cervin˜o,

2011; Ha-Brookshire & Yoon, 2012; Zolfagharian et al., 2014), the firm’s corporate headquarters (Marti´n & Cervin˜o, 2011), assembly (Ha-Brookshire & Yoon, 2012), design, parts (Ha-Brookshire & Yoon, 2012), and brands’ entry (Ha-Brookshire & Yoon, 2012)”. In another word, “the country with which a firm is associated” (Marti´n & Cervin˜o, 2011). The second category of definitions shows COO refers to “the image, reputation and stereotype (Kabadayi & Lerman, 2011), evaluation (Lee & Lee, 2011), facts (Marti´n & Cervin˜o, 2011) and previous public perceptions about the country’s people (Moradi & Zarei, 2012), production and marketing as a risk moderator or quality cue for consumers (Lee et al., 2013) that lead to favorable attitudes toward its products or brands (Marti´n & Cervin˜o, 2011)”. This research supports the second viewpoint. However, Lee & Lee (2011), show that COO refers to consumer’s attitudes about one or more of the following areas:

- Particular country in general;
- The overall of its production or
- Particular products offered by a particular country.

The literature of Ha-Brookshire & Yoon (2012), reports that, a more positive attitude towards foreign products among females, younger consumers and educated individuals earning high salaries. The following hypotheses cover significance testing of differences among perceptions of Saudi customers due to their demographic differences:

H1. There are significant differences among the perceptions of Iranian customers toward COO of vehicles from Korea, Iran according to Gender.

H2. There are significant overall differences among the perceptions of Iranian customers toward COO of vehicles from Iran and Korea, in general.

PERCEIVED QUALITY PQ

In attempting to treat a range of product attributes as discrete influences, there is an obvious danger in ignoring important interaction effects—for example those between “quality” and intrinsic and extrinsic product cues (Enis and Stafford 1969). In particular, the relationship between price and quality has been explored exhaustively (Gabor and Granger 1966; Leavitt 1964; McConnell 1968; Scitovsky 1944, 1945). Other factors such as branding and product composition also play some role in consumers’ choices.

Previous research (Gaedeke 1973; White and Cundiff 1978; Eroglu and Machleit 1989) has strongly suggested a close link between country of origin and perceptions of quality. The proposition that country of origin may act as a surrogate indicator of quality can be seen by examining the Z statistics (Boyd et al. 1985) in Table 2, showing the difference between the highest and lowest quality ratings for each product category. With the exception of tires (significant at 0.1), the difference is significant at the 0.05 level or better. Where products differed only in their country of origin, the difference in perceived quality was significant.

The quality of any product has two meaning, actual technical quality and PQ. Agus & Hajinoor (2012), show that, product quality performance includes conformance, performance, reliability and durability. Erdogmus & Turan (2012) define PQ as the consumer's judgment about the superiority of a product which is based on subjective perceptions. Pappu, Quester and Cooksey (2006) perceived country-of-origin has also reflects a different and varies level of perceived product quality. In their study, perceived quality of a brand from Finland is likely higher than the perceived quality level of a brand from Mexico or Hungary. In addition, Aaker (1991) had pointed out that perceived quality is actually an overall or superiority of the product and brand with respect to its intended purpose such as buying purpose .Parasuraman et al. (1985-1991), presented proposed models "SERVQUAL" and "SERVPERF" for the items of service's PQ as a comparison of consumer expectations with the actual performance. According to the literature of Wang (2013), there are numerous studies that suggest a positive correlation between PQ and PV. Wang (2013), reports that, PQ positively influences PV. Beneke et al. (2013), defines PQ as the way in which a customer views a product's brand equity and overall superiority compared to the available alternatives and the customer's attitude towards the overall brand experience as opposed to just a product's particular characteristics. The following hypothesis studies the influence of COO on PQ:

H3. COO has a significant impact on PQ of vehicles from (Iran/Korea), according to Iranian Customers.

PERCEIVED VALUE PV

To conceptualize Customer Value construct, two main approaches can be identified in the literature. The first approach defines PV as a one-dimensional construct, while the second approach defines PV as a multi-dimensional construct (Chen, 2013). PV is difficult to both define and measure (Beneke et al., 2013). It is a highly important construct that has influences on purchase intention (Beneke et al., 2013 and Munnukka & Jarvi, 2012). PV is one of the most important sources of competitive advantages (Mulki & Jaramillo, 2011). Customer value, as an individual's enduring feature in the consumption context, is different from the actual value (Choo et al., 2012). Customer value as "an interactive relativistic preference experience" and it is multifaceted (Munnukka & Jarvi, 2012). The literature of Chen (2013), suggests that PV research is still nascent and in the early stages of conceptual development. Therefore, various authors have emphasized a need for continuing research into the conceptualization of PV. Literatures show that there are four recurring characteristics of customer value: customer value is a subjective concept; trade-off between benefits and sacrifices; benefits and sacrifices can be multi-faceted and value perceptions are relative to competition (Chen, 2013). Quality has been found to be the most often investigated antecedent of value. There are structural relationships among value and other constructs (Chen, 2013). Value perceptions are thus critical to the firm given recent meta-analytic findings that demonstrate the significant impact of customer satisfaction on attitudinal loyalty and purchase intentions (Mulki & Jaramillo, 2011).

PV as customer' assessment for price-acceptability and worth of the product (Wang, 2013). It represents an overall mental

evaluation of product (Beneke et al., 2013). It includes the evaluation of product's attributes through the consumption process (Choo et al., 2012) and (Munnukka et al., 2013). The value perceptions are a cognitively-oriented appraisal that precedes customer satisfaction (Mulki & Jaramillo, 2011). Customer satisfaction is reached when the perception of benefits received meets or exceeds expectations (Mulki & Jaramillo, 2011). Common features of value includes the trade-off between costs and benefits (trade-off between quality and price; Rahikka et al., 2011; Choo et al., 2012; Mulki & Jaramillo, 2011; Smith, 2013) and the overall assessment of subjective worth, while taking into consideration suitable competitor alternatives (Beneke et al., 2013). Customers get benefits, quality, worth and utility. They pay price, costs and sacrifices. The buying process of high-tech products is generally more complex, and the suppliers often do not understand how customers make their purchasing decisions (Munnukka & Jarvi, 2012). Customer value as "the buyers' mental trade-off between the quality and benefits they perceive in the product relative to the sacrifice they perceive by paying the price" (Munnukka & Jarvi, 2012). Thus, PV is affected by both intrinsic and extrinsic dimensions of product quality and perceived price (Munnukka & Jarvi, 2012). A number of researchers note customer value as the focal factor needed to be incorporated into the pricing decision process (Munnukka et al., 2013). Both suppliers and customers are generally expected to be able to determine the economic value with a relatively high accuracy (Munnukka et al., 2013). On a high level of abstraction, PV is defined as the trade-off between the benefits "what is received" and sacrifices "what is given" in a market exchange (Chen, 2013; Mulki & Jaramillo, 2011). PV enhancement either by increasing the customer-perceived benefits or by reducing the sacrifices (Hakola, 2013). Customers come to expect a certain level of core product or service as "must haves" in their dealings with the firm and often look for "extras", firms have to add greater value to their products and services (Mulki & Jaramillo, 2011). Benefits and costs can have both monetary and non-monetary aspects (Mulki & Jaramillo, 2011).

The following hypotheses study the influences of COO on PV and the influences of PQ on PV:

H4. COO has a significant influence on PV of vehicles from, Iran/ Korea, according to Iranian Customers.

H5. PQ has a significant influence on PV of vehicles from Iran and Korea, according to Iranian Customers.

Figure 1 shows the structure of the research hypotheses as follows:

Figure 1. The structure of the research hypotheses

METHODOLOGY DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The structure of the questionnaire includes three dimensions, with fifteen items. All items measure the same points for each one of the two countries (Iran and Korea). First dimension includes three items for measuring the perceptions about COO. Second dimension includes four items for measuring the PV. Third dimension includes nine items for measuring the PQ. An adapted item was added to each dimension to test the multi regression of the items and their significance to measure the dimension. The questionnaire based on Likert scale on a five-point scale (1 representing "Strongly Disagree" to 5 representing "Strongly Agree") for measuring the participate level of agreement for each item. A part of items was added to the questionnaire to determine the demographic data of the participates for the analysis requirements and purposes. The constructs and items are detailed through.

Sampling method and sample size: Selective University is comprised of five colleges and eighty majors are taught in that. Totally, 26420 students study there. According to Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table, sample size was defined 381. Proportional Stratified sampling and systematic random sampling were applied. In the first place, based on Proportional Stratified sampling, sharing and distribution of questionnaires was done relative to the numbers of colleges. Afterwards, systematic random sampling was done in front of the college entrance gate to choose the respondents. With regard to the size of sample, 400 questionnaires were distributed, in total 381 completed questionnaire were obtained, that 193 questionnaire for Korean of vehicle and 188 questionnaire for Iran of vehicle gathered.

Reliability and Validity Analysis: To assess the reliability of questionnaire, Cronbach’s value was applied. The overall values of Cronbach Alpha is (a = 0.874). To examine that, a pre- test was carried out on sample with 55 respondents and 50 practical questionnaires were collected. The conclusion shows that Cronbach’s value of each variable was more than 0/7. The least significant reliability for research questionnaires is 0/7; thus, this questionnaire was recognized reliable.

Means of Items

Table 2 shows the mean for each item of the perceptions about COO. COO^{Korea} is the highest one and COO^{Iran} is the lowest one. The regression analysis shows the significance of the, all of them are significant. These items are highly correlated (R = 0.689: 0.768), they could explain significant percentages of COO construct (R^{Adjust} = 0.467: 0.

Table 1. Means & significance of COO items

lowest mean. The regression analysis shows the significance of the items, all of them are significant. These items are highly correlated (R = 0.564: 0.615), they could explain significant percentages of PV construct (R^{Adjust} = 0.316: 0.375).

Table 2. Means &significance of PV items

(*) Significant on the significance levels 0.05, 0.01 and 0.001

HYPOTHESIS ANALYSIS

Items	Means	
	Korean	Iran
PV ₁	3.84*	3.13*
PV ₂	3.59*	3.19*
Mean	3.89	3.10
R	0.616	0.562
R ^{Adjust}	0.377	0.312

We test and run the model by Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS, V. 21)after questionnaires data entry. The research includes 5 hypotheses. The hypothesis from H₁ covers the variation analysis of COO perceptions among Iranian customers toward products (in general) from Iran and Korea; according to demographic variable. These variable include gender. ANOVA analysis was used to explore the differences among the sample participates according to demographic variable. The results indicate significant effects about the differences of COO^{Korea} for Gender, because the mean of the males’ perceptions is significantly more than the mean of females’ perceptions, on the significance levels 0.05, 0.01 and 0.001.

Hypothesis H2 covers the exploring of differences among participates’ perceptions, according to COO, PQ and PV for the products (in general) from and Korea. ANOVA analysis was used for this test. The result indicate that there are significant differences among the persons’ perceptions of the sample for the products from or Korea on the significance levels (0.05; 0.01 and 0.001). COO^{Korea} are significantly more than COO^{Iran} and PQ^{KOREA} is significantly more than PQ^{Iran} and finally PV^{Korea} is significantly more than PV^{Iran}

Finally hypocrisies of H3 up 8 show the results of the correlation analysis between COO/PQ, COO/PV and PQ/PV.

Items	Means	
	USA	Korea
COO ₁	4.11*	3.76*
COO ₂	4.17*	3.53*
Mean	4.16	3.64
R	0.689	0.768
R ^{Adjust}	0.467	0.585

All correlations are significant on all significance levels 0.05, 0.01 and 0.001

(*) Significant on the significance levels 0.05, 0.01 and 0.001.

Table 2. Shows the mean for each item of the perception about PV and PV^{Korean} is the highest mean and PV^{Iran} is the

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

There is an increasing prevalence car products in Iran marketplace. Firms engaging in marketing these products should pay more attention to how consumers may react to these products. Firms planning a global production strategy or selecting a strategic partner overseas can seek to identify the optimal of the COO construct to maximize product quality and design quality perceptions. On the other hands, Understanding the guidelines that consumers use when evaluating the quality of products and value is imperative to manufacturers of consumer products and marketers in the retail industry and should be studied carefully before deciding on country-of-product origin. This study concluded that although country-of-origin is used as an external cue by consumers when evaluating product quality and value can influence consumers' evaluations.

So Marketers for products (including vehicles) from COO ^{Korea} should differ between males & females in their marketing plans & targeting, because males' perceptions about COO ^{Korea} are significantly better than females' perceptions. The research presents some contributions for the measurements of COO, PQ and PV for production in general or vehicles especially. Future research should consider bigger sample size and considering another demographic variables such as age, education, income. Ideally a larger sample size would provide a clearer Understanding of the relationships between the variables. Future researches should also include sample from more markets about more products from more COOs include japan, china.

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